

Sample Size Re-estimation for Comparison of Two Binomial Distributions Using One Interim Analysis with No Test

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Abstract

Sample Size Re-Estimation (SSRE) is examined for comparison of two binomial distributions in a double-blind randomized clinical trial, that includes one interim analysis (IA) for possible SSRE. The procedure for SSRE uses conditional power using asymptotic normality. With possible SSRE as the only goal, there is no hypothesis test at the IA. Details are presented for the situations with no stopping at the IA and with the option of stopping at the IA. The trial that motivated this research was designed for SSRE only and is presented as an example of an application of these procedures.

1. Introduction

The general procedure and results for the difference in probabilities for binomial distributions using asymptotic normality for two treatments in a blinded parallel-group trial (also referred to as groups below) are given below. Unless specified otherwise, all sample sizes are per group, and all sample sizes are assumed to be the same for the two treatments. All two-sided tests will be performed at level α using one-sided tests at level $\alpha/2$. Let $z(\phi) = 100(1-\phi)$ -th quantile of the standard normal distribution $N(0,1)$, so $z(\gamma) = \Phi^{-1}(1-\gamma)$, where Φ is the cdf of the $N(0,1)$ distribution.

One unblinded interim analysis (IA) will be performed after $2N_I$ subjects have response (0 or 1) available for analysis, where the sample sizes are assumed to be N_I subjects per treatment, which is an approximation because the blind is maintained prior to the IA. In practice, this IA would be conducted with the guidance of an independent committee. For the trial that motivated this research, the two treatments (an experimental treatment and a control) are to be compared with respect to the occurrence of an unfavorable event; however, the results are also applicable to comparison with respect to the occurrence of a favorable event. Also in that trial, the event would occur shortly after treatment initiation, so enrollment could be terminated during the IA and that assumption is also made here. The Sponsor did not want to stop the trial at the IA for the lack of efficacy (futility) or superiority and, in either case, to continue the trial to collect additional safety data for the experimental treatment.

Let π_1 and π_0 be the “assumed” true probabilities of response for the two treatments. These are the probabilities at which it is desired to control the power. The corresponding estimates of π_1 and π_0 are the proportions p_{1I} and p_{0I} , p_{1P} and p_{0P} , p_{1F} and p_{0F} from the IA, post-IA, and Final Analysis (FA), respectively. Let $\Delta = \pi_0 - \pi_1$ and $R = \pi_1(1-\pi_1) + \pi_0(1-\pi_0)$.

Let N_F be actual sample size per group for the FA as determined by the decision at the IA, and $N_P = N_F - N_I$ denote the number of patients enrolled after the IA, if any. Further, let $R_I = p_{1I}(1-p_{1I}) + p_{0I}(1-p_{0I})$, $R_P = p_{1P}(1-p_{1P}) + p_{0P}(1-p_{0P})$, and $R_F = p_{1F}(1-p_{1F}) + p_{0F}(1-p_{0F})$ be the estimates of R from the IA, post-IA, and FA, respectively, and let $D_I = p_{0I} - p_{1I}$, $D_P = p_{0P} - p_{1P}$, and $D_F = p_{0F} - p_{1F}$ denote the corresponding estimates of Δ . The between-treatment difference in the numbers of events prior to the IA is $N_I D_I$; similarly, $N_P D_P$ for post-IA and $N_F D_F$ for the FA.

Also, let $T_I = N_I^{1/2} D_I / R_I^{1/2}$, $T_P = N_P^{1/2} D_P / R_P^{1/2}$, and $T_F = N_F^{1/2} D_F / R_F^{1/2}$ be the test statistics from the IA, post-IA, and FA, respectively, so $T_I - N_I^{1/2} \Delta / R_I^{1/2}$, $T_P - N_P^{1/2} \Delta / R_P^{1/2}$, and $T_F - N_F^{1/2} \Delta / R_F^{1/2}$ have asymptotic $N(0,1)$ distributions. If responses for all subjects enrolled prior to the IA are available to be included in the IA, then T_I and T_P are independent. This was true in the motivating example, a trial in neonates, with all responses occurring shortly after birth; thus there is no overrun, as discussed in Hampson and Jennison (2013) and Baldi, Azzolina, et al (2020). Although the procedure presented here does not explicitly incorporate overrun, it could be incorporated with straightforward revisions

To test $H_0: \Delta=0$ against $H_1: \Delta \neq 0$ at level α at the FA, the test will be performed at level $\alpha/2$ (one-sided) as: Reject H_0 if $T_F \geq z(\alpha/2)$. To ensure power $1-\beta$ with assumed values π_1 and π_0 , the trial is planned for $N = \lceil R(Q/\Delta)^2 \rceil$ observations per group where $Q = z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$ where $\lceil x \rceil$ is the smallest integer $\geq x$. The trial that motivated this research was designed to compare the two treatments with respect to the occurrence of an unfavorable event, so a one-sided test at level α could be appropriate. However, as most of the research on related topics. a one-sided test at level $\alpha/2$ is used for a two-sided test at level α .

An adaptive approach using the conditional power of the test at FA given the observations from the IA is considered. Details are presented for the situations with no stopping at the IA (Part A) and with the option of stopping at the IA (Part B). The situation is similar to that considered by Cui, Hung, and Wang (1999) and Mehta and Pocock (2011), as discussed in Gao, Ware, and Mehta (2008). Recent reviews of SSRE are given in Uemura et al (2017) and Boumendil et al (2024), and have also been discussed in the nonstatistical literature such as the recent presentation in psychological research by Vankelecom et al (2024). Unlike much of the previous research, here there is no test at the only IA. The stopping rules are based on results at the IA without a test because the sponsor did not want to stop the study.

2. Conditional Power

The conditional power (CP) is the power of the test at FA, conditioned on the results from the IA. The CP is used for the decision at the IA and can be expressed in terms of $T_I = N_I^{1/2} D_I / R_I^{1/2}$.

For fixed $N_F > N_I$, $N_F D_F = N_I D_I + N_P D_P$, so the approximate power for the test at the FA is

$$\begin{aligned} P\{T_F \geq z(\alpha/2) | I_A\} &= P\{N_I^{1/2} R_I^{1/2} T_I + N_P^{1/2} R_P^{1/2} T_P \geq N_F^{1/2} R_F^{1/2} z(\alpha/2)\} \\ &= P\{N_P^{1/2} R_P^{1/2} T_P \geq N_F^{1/2} R_F^{1/2} z(\alpha/2) - N_I^{1/2} R_I^{1/2} T_I\} \\ &= P\{T_P - N_P^{1/2} \Delta / R_P^{1/2} \geq [N_F^{1/2} R_F^{1/2} z(\alpha/2) - N_I^{1/2} R_I^{1/2} T_I - N_P \Delta] / N_P^{1/2} R_P^{1/2}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $T_P - N_P^{1/2} \Delta / R_P^{1/2}$ has an asymptotic standard normal distribution, the power is approximately

$$\begin{aligned} &1 - \Phi\left(\frac{N_F R_F / N_P R_P^{1/2} z(\alpha/2) - (N_I R_I / N_P R_P)^{1/2} T_I - (N_P / R_P)^{1/2} \Delta}{(N_P / R_P)^{1/2} \Delta + (N_I R_I / N_P R_P)^{1/2} T_I - (N_F R_F / N_P R_P)^{1/2} z(\alpha/2)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, equating CP at the estimate observed at the IA,

$$\begin{aligned} CP(D_I | N_F) &= \Phi\left(\frac{(R_I / R_P)^{1/2} T_I N_F / (N_I N_P)^{1/2} - (R_F / R_P)^{1/2} (N_F / N_P)^{1/2} z(\alpha/2)}{(R_I / R_P)^{1/2} T_I / (v(1-v))^{1/2} - (R_F / R_P)^{1/2} z(\alpha/2) / (1-v)^{1/2}}\right), \text{ where } v = N_I / N_F < 1. \end{aligned}$$

$CP(D_I | N_F)$ depends on R_F and R_P , so CP cannot be used at the IA as presented. To remove this dependence, the asymptotic approximation $R_F = R_I = R_P$ is imposed. An alternative to the approximation $R_F = R_I = R_P$ is the arc-sine transformation used for comparison of several treatments to a control for binomial distributions by Bristol (1989, 1993) and described in Desu and Raghavarao (1990), Shiraishi (2022), and elsewhere. It is mentioned for a single binomial

distribution by Jennison and Turnbull (2000) without details. Details of the use of this transformation for the current problem are being examined and will be presented elsewhere. With $v=N_I/N_F < 1$,

$CP(D_I|N_F) = \Phi((T_I - v^{1/2}z(\alpha/2))/v^{1/2}(1-v)^{1/2})$, so the CP for the planned sample size is

$CP(D_I|N) = \Phi((T_I - t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2))/t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2})$,

where $t=N_I/N$, the relative timing of the IA. $CP(D_I|N)$ is used for decision making at the IA, where t is specified by design as both N_I and N are specified in the protocol.

3. Part A (No stopping at the IA)

3.1 Decision at the IA

The options for the decision at the IA are:

Continue with a re-estimated sample size (RESS) or

Continue as planned.

Let P_2 be a fixed constant with $P_2 < 1 - \beta$. If $CP(D_I|N) > P_2$, then the study will continue as planned. If $CP(D_I|N) \leq P_2$, then the sample size will be re-estimated. If $T_I < t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2)$, then the procedure based on conditional power cannot be used because $CP(D_I|N) < 0.5$. There is no solution to this because it depends on the data from the IA. The Sponsor was informed of this and decided to ignore it because it would be a stopping rule for the IA and was (optimistically) willing to assume that it would not occur. In the following, it is assumed that $T_I \geq t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2)$. Thus the options for the decision at the IA are:

Continue with a RESS if $CP(D_I|N) \leq P_2$ or

Continue as planned if $CP(D_I|N) > P_2$.

If the sample size is re-estimated, let N_R denote the RESS, defined as the largest N_F such that $CP(D_I|N_F) \leq P_2$, so N_R satisfies $T_I - v^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) \leq v^{1/2}(1-v)^{1/2}z(1-P_2)$ where $v=N_I/N_R$. Thus $T_I \leq v^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + v^{1/2}(1-v)^{1/2}z(1-P_2)$, which can be solved iteratively when T_I is observed.

3.2 Example

The following example motivated this research, but details are omitted for proprietary reasons. The study was designed to compare a treatment to a control with respect to the occurrence of an unfavorable event. Using the methodology presented in Section 2, namely $N = \langle R(Q/\Delta)^2 \rangle$ with $Q = z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta) = 3.24$, a sample size of $N = 121$ subjects per group is required to be included in the primary analysis to ensure that the test with level 0.05 (two-sided) would have power of 90% ($\beta = 0.1$) for $\pi_0 = 0.5$ and $\pi_1 = 0.3$. The decision at IA was determined by $P_2 = 0.8$. The planned sample size was $N = 125$ subjects per group with an IA at $N_I = 85$ ($t = 0.680$) subjects per group.

The Sponsor also wanted investigation of the consequences of 80% power. Then, with $\Delta = \pi_0 - \pi_1 = 0.2$, $R = \pi_1(1 - \pi_1) + \pi_0(1 - \pi_0) = 0.46$, and $Q = z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta) = 2.80$, the sample size per group is $N = \langle R(Q/\Delta)^2 \rangle = 91$. It was decided that the sample size per group would be $N = 95$ with an IA at 65 ($t = 0.684$) subjects per group.

However, with these values, there is no solution with $T_I \geq t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) = 1.62$ and $N_R \geq N$. A solution exists only for extreme situations; for example, with $N = 95$, $N_I = 47$ ($t = 0.494$), $P_2 = 0.5$, and $\beta = 0.01$, the solution is $N_R = 95$ for $T_I = 1.38$.

4. Part B (includes option of stopping at the IA)

4.1 Decision at the IA

The options for the decision at the IA are:

- Continue with a RESS;
- Continue as planned;
- Stop for futility; or
- Stop for superiority.

Let $P1$ and $P2$ be specified values with $P1 < P2$, $P1 < 0.5 < \text{MIN}(1-\beta, P2)$. If $CP(D_I|N) < P1$, then $CP(D_I|N)$ is unacceptably low, so the study is stopped for futility; if $CP(D_I|N) > P2$, then $CP(D_I|N)$ is sufficiently large, so the study will continue as planned. The constraint that $P1 < 0.5 < 1-\beta$ is discussed in Uemura et al (2008). If $P1 \leq CP(D_I|N) \leq P2$, then the RESS (N_R) will be used if $N_R \leq N_M$, where N_M is a specified constant, usually chosen by economic constraints.

If $T_I \geq z(\alpha/2)$, then it would be unethical to continue enrollment after the IA because efficacy has been established, so $N_F = N_I$ and $T_F = T_I$. In this case, $CP(D_I|N_F) = CP(D_I|N_I) = P\{T_I \geq z(\alpha/2)\}$; if this probability $\geq 1-\beta$, $T_I \geq z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$ and the study will be stopped for superiority at the IA.

The study will be stopped for futility if $CP(D_I|N) < P1$ or the RESS satisfies $N_R > N_M$, which is equivalent to $T_I < (N_I/N_M)^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + (N_I(N_M - N_I))^{1/2}z(\beta)/N_M$ since $CP(D_I|N_M) < 1-\beta$. Finally SSRE will be performed if $P1 \leq CP(D_I|N) < P2$ and $CP(D_I|N) < 1-\beta$, and $N_R \leq N_M$. Thus, the options for the decision at the IA with the resultant sample size at the FA are:

- Continue using SSRE with $N_F = N_R$ if $P1 \leq CP(D_I|N) < \text{MAX}(P2, 1-\beta)$ and $N_R \leq N_M$;
- Continue as planned (CAP) with $N_F = N$ if $CP(D_I|N) \geq \text{MAX}(P2, 1-\beta)$ and $T_I < z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$;
- Stop for futility (FUT) with $N_F = N_I$ if $CP(D_I|N) < P1$ or $N_R > N_M$; or
- Stop for superiority (SUP) with $N_F = N_I$ if $T_I \geq z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$.

Equivalently, with $u = N_I/N_M$, the options in terms of T_I are:

- SSRE if $\text{MAX}\{t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(1-P1), u^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + u^{1/2}(1-u)^{1/2}z(\beta)\} \leq T_I < \text{MAX}\{t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(1-P2), t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(\beta)\}$;
- CAP if $\text{MAX}\{t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(1-P2), t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(\beta)\} \leq T_I < z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$;
- FUT if $T_I < \text{MAX}\{t^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + t^{1/2}(1-t)^{1/2}z(1-P1), u^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + u^{1/2}(1-u)^{1/2}z(\beta)\}$; or
- SUP if $T_I \geq z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$.

Let $C(x, P) = x^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + x^{1/2}(1-x)^{1/2}z(1-P)$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$. Then the options are

- SSRE if $\text{MAX}\{C(t, P1), C(u, 1-\beta)\} \leq T_I < \text{MAX}\{C(t, P2), C(t, 1-\beta)\}$;
- CAP if $\text{MAX}\{C(t, P2), C(t, 1-\beta)\} \leq T_I < z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$;
- FUT if $T_I < \text{MAX}\{C(t, P1), C(u, 1-\beta)\}$; or
- SUP if $T_I \geq z(\alpha/2) + z(\beta)$.

4.2 Determination of RESS

If the sample size is re-estimated, let $h(v) = v^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + v^{1/2}(1-v)^{1/2}z(\beta) - T_I$, so the goal is to determine the solution to $h(v) = 0$. The derivative of $h(v)$ is $h'(v) = [(1-v)^{1/2}z(\alpha/2) + (1-2v)z(\beta)] / 2v^{1/2}(1-v)^{1/2}$. The solution to $h(v) = 0$ can be obtained using the Newton-Raphson method, iterating $v_{n+1} = v_n - h(v_n)/h'(v_n)$ until $|h(v_n)| < \epsilon$ with an initial value v_1 for specified small ϵ ($v_1 = 0.5$ and $\epsilon = 0.0001$ were used here). Then the RESS is $N_R = N_I/v^*$, where v^* is the solution to $h(v^*) = 0$, which also depends on T_I . The use of the Newton-Raphson method is shown in detail in the example in Section 4.3.

The RESS (N_R) is given in the following table for these input parameters using the Newton-Raphson technique for $T_I=0.40$ (0.04) 1.20. for $\beta=0.1$ and $\beta=0.2$. The convergence is rapid with $\varepsilon=0.0001$ and independent of any meaningful initial value v_1 . This can also be used to determine the solution for Part A when a solution exists

4.3 Example

The following example motivated this research, but details are omitted for proprietary reasons. The study was designed to compare a treatment to a control with respect to the occurrence of an unfavorable event. Using the methodology presented in Section 2, namely $N = \lceil R(Q/\Delta)^2 \rceil$, a sample size of $N=121$ subjects per group is required to be included in the primary analysis to ensure that the test with level 0.05 (two-sided) would have power of 90% ($\beta=0.1$) for $\pi_0=0.5$ and $\pi_1=0.3$. It was decided to enroll $N=125$ subjects per group with the IA at 170 subjects ($N_I=85$ subjects per group) and a maximum RESS of $N_M=200$ subjects per group. The bounds on the decision at the IA are specified to be $P1=0.3$ and $P2=0.8$. With $t=N_I/N=85/125=0.68$, $u=N_I/N_M=85/200=0.425$, the options are

- SSRE if $1.91 \leq T_I < 2.21$;
- CAP if $2.21 \leq T_I < 3.24$;
- FUT if $T_I < 1.91$; or
- SUP if $T_I \geq 3.24$.

The Sponsor also wanted investigation of the consequences of 80% power. Then, with $\Delta=\pi_0-\pi_1=0.2$, $R=\pi_1(1-\pi_1)+\pi_0(1-\pi_0)=0.46$, and $Q=z(\alpha/2)+z(\beta)=2.80$, the sample size per group is $N = \lceil R(Q/\Delta)^2 \rceil = 91$. It was decided that the sample size per group would be $N=95$ with an IA at 65/group. The maximum RESS is specified to be $N_M=150$ /group. These input parameters result in $t=N_I/N=65/95=0.684$ and $u=N_I/N_M=65/150=0.433$, which are very close to those for 90% power. In this case, the options are

- SSRE if $1.71 \leq T_I < 2.01$;
- CAP if $2.01 \leq T_I < 2.80$;
- FUT if $T_I < 1.71$; or
- SUP if $T_I \geq 2.80$.

Given T_I , the RESS is $N_R=N_I/v^*$, where v^* is given in the following table. Because N_I/N_M and N_I/N are approximately the same for $\beta=0.1$ and $\beta=0.2$ and these are the bounds on the solution, the same values of v^* , with different values of T_I are obtained. For $\beta=0.1$, the RESS is provided for $T_I=1.93$ to 2.21 by 0.02 and $T_I=1.912$ and $T_I=2.215$, with the latter two being the solutions to $N_R=200$ and $N_R=125$, respectively. For $\beta=0.2$, the RESS is provided for $T_I=1.71$ to 1.99 by 0.02 and $T_I=2.013$, with the latter being the solution to $N_R=95$. Thus $125 \leq N_R \leq 200$ for $\beta=0.1$ and $95 \leq N_R \leq 150$ for $\beta=0.2$ subject to round-off error in the bounds, depending on the value of T_I .

Table 1: Determination of RESS (N_R) = N_I/v per group
 ($\alpha=0.05$, $P1=0.3$, $P2=0.8$)

	$\beta=0.1, N_I=85, N=125, N_M=200$		$\beta=0.2, N_I=65, N=95, N_M=150$	
$v^* = N_I/N_R$	T_I	N_R	T_I	N_R
0.43	1.912	200	-	-
0.44	1.93	195	1.71	150
0.45	1.95	190	1.73	146
0.46	1.97	185	1.75	142
0.47	1.99	180	1.77	138
0.49	2.01	175	1.79	134
0.50	2.03	170	1.81	130
0.52	2.05	165	1.83	126
0.53	2.07	160	1.85	123
0.55	2.09	155	1.87	119
0.57	2.11	151	1.89	116
0.58	2.13	146	1.91	112
0.60	2.15	141	1.93	109
0.63	2.17	136	1.95	106
0.65	2.19	132	1.97	102
0.67	2.21	127	1.99	99
0.68	2.215	125	2.013	95

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